

Stabilities of Bivalent Metal Chelates of 3-Hydroxy-3-Ethyl-1-*p*-Chloro and -1-*o*-Chlorophenyltriazenes

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Stabilities of palladium, copper, nickel, zinc and manganese chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-ethyl-1-*p*-chloro and-1-*o*-chlorophenyl triazenes have been determined in 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture by employing Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique. The titration medium was maintained at a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M potassium chloride and at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

In the previous communication¹, the stabilities of palladium, copper, nickel, zinc and manganese chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-phenyl-1-*p*-acetylphenyltriazene have been reported. Substitution of different groups in different positions of the hydroxytriazene molecule gave interesting results. The present investigation deals with the influence of chloro group at ortho and para positions of 3-hydroxy-3-ethyl-1-phenyltriazene upon the the stabilities of metal chelates formed by them.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydroxytriazenes were prepared by the method given by Sogani and Dugar². Bjerrum-Calvin³ pH titration technique was employed for determining stability

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

1. D. N. Purohit and N. C. Sogani, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 20.
2. S. M. Dugar and N. C. Sogani, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 289.
3. M. Calvin and N. C. Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 0, 3270.

constants of metal chelates. Other experimental details are the same as described in the earlier communication. The titration curve for these chelating agents with different metal ions are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Calculations : It has been observed that when the values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ of the metal chelate differ by less than one unit (as in the case of palladium and copper chelates of these ligands) the result obtained by the least-squares method and by the method of interpolation at $1/2 \bar{n}$ values show a slight variation. For such cases the method of least squares is preferred. However, in cases, where $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ differ by more than one unit (as in case of nickel, zinc and manganese chelates of these ligands), the method of interpolation at $1/2 \bar{n}$ values also give correct results. Hence, the stabilities of palladium and chelates were calculated by the method of least squares and the stabilities of nickel, zinc and manganese by the method of interpolation at $1/2 \bar{n}$ values, which is simpler than the former.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

The formation curves of nickel, zinc and manganese chelates of 3-hydroxy 3-ethyl-1-p-chloro-and 1-o-chlorophenyltriazenes are given in Figs 3 & 4. The values of $\log k_1$, $\log k_2$ and $\log k_1 k_2$ are read from the curves and given in table 1. The results are consistent within ± 0.02 .

The values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ for palladium and copper were calculated by the methods of least squares.

The values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_1 k_2$ for metal chelates of both the hydroxy-triazenes are given in table 1.

TABLE 1

Meta-1	Stability of metal chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-ethyl-1-p-chloro phenyltriazene		Stability of metal chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-ethyl-1-o-chloro-phenyltriazene	
	$\log k_1$	$\log k_1 k_2$	$\log k_1$	$\log k_1 k_2$
Palladium	10.68	20.66	10.49	20.46
Copper	10.63	20.38	10.38	19.85
Nickel	7.58	13.48	7.32	13.01
Zinc	6.35	10.96	5.94	10.29
Manganese	5.94	10.14	5.79	9.78

DISCUSSION

For the sake of simplicity, only the stabilities of palladium chelates with different hydroxytriazenes are discussed. A comparison of the values of the overall stability constants of the palladium chelates of para-chloro ($\log k_1 k_2 = 20.66$) and ortho-chloro ($\log k_1 k_2 = 20.46$) with the parent hydroxytriazene ⁴($\log k_1 k_2 = 22.23$) reveals that chloro substitution lowers the stability of the resulting chelates. The -I effect of the halogen lowers the pK_a values of the chloro-substituted hydroxytriazenes⁵ (pK_a of parent compound = 12.28, para-chloro substituted = 11.56 and ortho-chloro = 11.44) and hence the stabilities of their metal chelates. This group in the ortho position exerts greater influence than in the para-position due to the nearness of -I effect. +M effect of the chloro-groups in the present cases does not seem to be operative, otherwise the stabilities of the chelates formed by substituted hydroxytriazenes would have been higher than the parent compound.

The authors express their gratitude to Professor R. C. Mehrotra for providing facilities in the Department and to the University Grants Commission for a research fellowship to one of them (S. M. D).

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Received, October 4, 1967.

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